

**Complicated Systemic Barriers: The Experiences of Immigrant
Groups Across Education, Health Care, and the Labor Force**

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Abstract

Throughout many generations, Hispanic/Latino, Asian, and African American immigrants have shared stories of oppression and the troubles they've faced migrating to a new country. This entails new social norms, structures, and the difficulty of adapting to this new style of living. Although some may quickly acclimate to society they face, others have firsthand witnessed the barriers in place that perhaps purposely, intend to complicate their integration. My research investigated their experiences in various social domains, specially focusing on educational institutions, healthcare settings, and the labor force. I investigated how these domains relate to one another, and their impact on the mental health of these immigrant groups. Upon analyzing a variety of ethnographic and correlational studies, as well as mixed methods and a multitude of surveys and interviews in my research, I found that these barriers are a large predictor of life satisfaction, social mobility, and mental health status. Thus, governmental policies and social shifts that promote inclusion eliminate stigmas, and deliver services in an organized and equitable way, would lessen the barriers they face across many social emotional contexts. These findings are significant because they raise awareness to social issues that create burdens to the lives of newcomers and the necessary measures to alleviate them. They also highlight the resilience of immigrant family units that despite many obstacles, become assets to the host country they decide to enter.

Keywords: systemic barriers, acculturation, oppression, mental health, social mobility, immigrant status.

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Intro

Throughout history, immigration has been fueled by a number of events, including expanding frontiers of the Americas, economic depressions, industrial revolutions, and even a search for religious and political freedom. This spiked my interest to learn more in depth about why certain groups, including Asian Americans, African Americans, and my own group, Hispanic Latino families decide to put their life at risk migrating to the United States. Do the pros and “opportunities” outweigh the cons? Most importantly, will they find luck and prosperity as they settle into life in their new country? I chose this topic to research because I also was a daughter of immigrants who experienced unforeseen barriers and hardships growing up, wondering if it had anything to do with where I had come from. Was it my fault? Was I not worthy of receiving the same enriching opportunities and services as my peers? Aside from language and cultural divides, I knew I had a long road ahead of me and that I’d have to be strong and work twice as hard if I wanted to have social mobility in the U.S. Through my research, I’ve come up with the conclusion that these barriers are a large predictor of life satisfaction, social mobility, and have strong implications on mental health. These immigrant groups face a lot of challenges across many social domains, which commonly puts them at a disadvantage in education, the workforce, and mental health issues. Although, there are exceptions. Here specifically I will research how these barriers affect the outcomes of Hispanic/Latinos, Asian Americans, and African Americans. I wish to uplift these communities and hope more advances will be done in the near future to improve their life chances.

Background

Increasing patterns of immigration don't come without consequence. There has been and continues to be an uproar and contentious feelings about the short and long term effects of this influx of immigrants into the country. As a result, coherent immigration policies and pieces of legislation have also experienced many shifts because of objectives clouded with bias (economic) and discrimination. To reiterate, since the 18th century, immigration and naturalization was fueled by desires to increase trade surpluses and was solely based on characteristics of class, status, and race. Some individuals were also behind the protection of citizenship, such that those deemed undesirable for the government and society, would be unable to own real estate, and have limited political and economic rights. With the passing of the 1740 Plantation Act, settlement and naturalization spiked and the act incentivized immigration.

Fast forward to today, multitudes of families from disadvantaged backgrounds continue to leave their native land to escape extreme poverty, famine, job shortages, and in search for new opportunities for their families to name a few. Even in the 21st century, patterns of immigration into the U.S have continued with significant numbers. And although it's evident that the U.S immigration system is flawed, it's still important to contextualize efforts from Congress to create opportunities for new immigrants. For example, the greatest and most beneficial legislation that has passed thus far, has been DACA. This is the consideration of Deferred Action for Childhood Arrivals of 2012, subject to approval, an administrative relief that enables immigrant individuals to remain in the country with protection against deportation, and access to different employment and economic benefits. Although an injunction from the U.S District Court in 2021 remains in effect to limit benefits accessed by beneficiaries and new applicants, it's essential to consider that

efforts like these with support of higher courts and governmental bodies, are definitely possible and necessary for a social justice agenda.

Research Aims and Objectives

Overall Aim: This research seeks to analyze the systemic barriers, as well as their long and short term effects on the experiences of immigrant children and their families, as well as the differences faced amongst these groups themselves.

Specific Objectives:

- To examine tensions and barriers in educational settings occupied by immigrant groups throughout their schooling years
- To analyze the barriers and conflicts that negatively impact/impede the social mobility of immigrants in terms of labor and social class.
- To investigate the barriers that create disparities in healthcare that hinder health outcomes for years after.

Methodology

Much of my conclusions about immigrant experiences in relation to these barriers in healthcare, education, and the workforce are derived from case studies, questionnaires and surveys conducted from within a range of 15 years to get a more comprehensive view of how their experiences may differ from those in contemporary times. Health and school records have also been examined to get clinical data on recent/latest visits with healthcare professionals. I found that these systemic barriers are a large predictor of life satisfaction, social mobility, and mental health status. These studies were limited to participants from Hispanic/Latino, Asian,

African descent, and were derived from peer-reviewed articles dating as far as 2007. Some of the questions that drove my research were: What are the implications of these barriers in terms of psychological and emotional distress? How do immigrant groups differ in their social mobility and educational attainment in relation to the barriers they come across?

Barriers in Healthcare

Eligibility

Legal status and social class determines Hispanic/Latino rights to developmental and social services that would otherwise be immediate basic rights for citizens. Although state and local governments have taken initiatives to increase funding for insurance coverage like AB-133 and the CARES ACT, states like Georgia and Virginia have taken steps back (Okie, 2007). The CARES act (Community assistance, Recovery, and Empowerment Act) was a 2020 piece of federal legislation that allocated emergency funds to alleviate the health care crisis faced by families, a policy that would specifically be beneficial for undocumented and low income groups. This was especially helpful for vulnerable Californians to receive behavioral health, mental health services, and even assistance for those facing homelessness. The assembly bill 133 would also be a policy that strived to provide a prevention focused approach and equitable health care at a higher standard. Yet, a study found that only about 1.5% of United States health coverage spending comes from immigrant families, meaning they are left out of preventive services like immunizations, family planning, and prenatal care (Salami et al., 2020). Insurance premiums and out of pocket medical care are often too expensive, so timely referrals from specialists are things that are put off until the condition or disease is advanced to treat. In fact, seven in ten Hispanic immigrants participating in a 2022 survey about their beliefs about health

risks in their community recall not seeing a physician in the last year for their pre-existing conditions (Okie, 2007).

This percentage had drastically changed with the consideration of citizenship status, with 72% of Hispanics reporting seeing a doctor in primary care, a notable difference than those with immigrant status (Okie, 2007). For example, Latinos and other racial/ethnic minorities have a higher risk and prevalence of certain diseases like diabetes, heart disease, cancer, liver disease, high blood pressure, and other high care maintenance conditions. They are the leading causes of death for these groups, according to the Centers for Disease and Prevention, because of out-of-pocket expense burdens that implicate prescription drugs and inpatient stays for short and long term treatment and management for these diseases (Okie, 2007). These adverse conditions have preventative measures even with simple diagnostic efforts, but mortality rates are heightened for Hispanics because they'll seek medical interventions until the end stages of the illness.

For example, their prevalence for hypertension related conditions can be a precursor for future heart failure or strokes, but not attending routine check ups can prevent them from obtaining things like diuretics, vasodilators, ACE inhibitors, or even medical advice for lifestyle changes that'll decrease the progression of the condition (Okie, 2007). Hispanic prevalence for liver disease is further propagated by their increased exposure to things like hepatitis viruses (sometimes from poor living conditions in povertic immigrant communities), obesity, and alcoholism, making them 40% more likely to pass away when compared to non-Hispanic groups (Okie, 2007). Metabolic interventions, antivirals, and diagnosis can prevent the severity of it from reaching transplant needed status, but again, these are things rarely obtained due to late courses of action for seeking care. After care for things like transplantation and post care dialysis

in liver disease are sometimes well within their reach.

So what's the reason for these differences in healthcare utilization? Hispanic immigrants aren't able to qualify for "affordable" health care packages outside the marketplace due to eligibility restrictions, and out of pocket services are beyond their reach, all which contribute to the health disparities we see amongst these groups and the effects on the 3.2 million individuals that still don't have any insurance in California alone (Salami et al., 2020). Lawful status in the country can get you access to Marketplace insurance, but those immigrants with "higher" annual income (still low for living wage) than the acceptable threshold for eligibility will have a tougher time finding a suitable premium according to their health needs and budget. Age and residential living status, household size, amongst other federal eligibility rules that are rigidly placed, also contribute to 50% of their likelihood in the year 2023, to be uninsured when compared to naturalized or U.S born citizens (Salami et al., 2020). This leaves immigrants with access only to emergency services and even with early detection and a medication regimen established for Hispanic patients, thorough adherence is very unlikely due to insurance programs (like Medicare) inability to provide affordable prescriptions in a timely manner. This coverage would of course be determined by state initiatives, with some immigrants having to wait 5 year periods for approval for a procedure, and some never getting treatment at all. As a result, low quality insurance programs for Hispanic immigrants deprive them of things like in-home support services, preventative screenings, immunosuppressive treatments, and treatment for psychological and mental health (Salami et al., 2020). It's important to note that Congress needs to work together with racial equity advocates, representatives and organizations for low income, homeless, undocumented and disabled individuals because they seem to be the most left out of these policies.

Medical Deserts

Medical deserts are yet another barrier that Hispanic/Latino and African immigrant communities face, further contributing to the deteriorated health outcomes they're likely to experience. A "medical desert" is defined as a place where adequate access to healthcare facilities, clinics, pharmacies, trauma centers, and low cost health centers are scarce (Vitello, 2023). Things that one must consider is, accommodation (how fast can a patient be seen), availability (are there enough healthcare providers to meet demands of the population), and other distinct areas including affordability, and accessibility. According to Pennic, an advisor for executive leaders in top national health systems and IT strategist, about 80% of the United States counties don't have appropriate access to healthcare centers (Vitello, 2023). These problems with infrastructure are more critical for Latinos, who are 2.5 times more likely to reside in a health desert than their peers. This includes states like Texas, Florida, Arizona, which would require them to drive close to 15 hours to access care or even having to wait months to be able to schedule appointments with a health professional (Vitello, 2023). Some facilities available to them don't always have adequate supply of services, medications, or even sufficient personnel to meet the demands and needs of the populations they serve. As a result, these medically underserved areas are more likely to experience higher mortality levels at a young age due to the lack of qualitative services or specialists that would otherwise be required for optimal health.

Next, medical deserts also contribute to the grave issue of having deterred health for African immigrants, such as in the case of pulmonary diseases that require early detection if one wants to prevent their development into asthma. Medical deserts also impact immigrant

women's reproductive and sexual health, as well as that of pregnant mothers. Hispanic/Latino and even African female immigrants in a 2020 questionnaire about their satisfaction with accessing preventative services and being able to exercise their reproductive rights, claimed that they weren't able to access birth control, contraceptives, or attend routine checkups for mammograms or cervical cancer screenings because clinic were too far away from their reach (Vitello, 2023). Even in the case of abortions, female immigrants run the risk of mortality because of turning to illegal/ clandestine abortions and procedures as their last chance. On a small scale, a proposed solution to this inequality or barrier in healthcare, is telemedicine, so this could be providing communities with centers where they could access technology that enables them to communicate with physicians remotely, saving them time and cost of visiting an office far away. On a larger scale, there should be more funding from the Department of Health Care Services, and a higher state budget from Newsom's annual state plans allocated to professional training for staff, emergency responses, and creating safer, more accessible procedures to women regardless of age and status. This could even just mean having more professional development for medical center personnel and receiving funds to ensure facilities have enough equipment and medications to accommodate their needs.

Health Literacy

One of the greatest contributors to not having access to medical services is also the difficulty in the enrollment processes and lack of guidance for it. Many African and Hispanic immigrants have confusion and misinformation in regards to programs like Medi-Cal, or even refrain from applying because they aren't aware of their eligibility. A study found that expenses for health care for immigrant children were 86% lower than those of U. S citizens (Okie, 2007).

This is because the parents of immigrant children may lack expertise or resources to apply to care plans and because of unjust Medicaid thresholds that may only cover emergency services. It's also common for enrollment periods to close before immigrants get a chance to consider all their options and apply. This correlates with "health literacy", which is defined as a person's knowledge and ability to seek, understand, and use services, information, and systems available to them to achieve good health (Okie. 2007). Deductibles, eligibility provisions, and copays are often things these groups are unable to comprehend, sometimes being magnified with application forms not available in their native language. In a survey conducted by Pew Research Center in 2021, with Hispanic immigrants both men and women ranging from 18 to 65 years of age, 49% claimed the process of applying to receive medical assistance in centers, hospitals, or even insurance applications was very/and/or somewhat complicated to understand (Nadeem & Nadeem, 2024). This is also similar to their experiences with public programs that aim to provide nutritional and economic support for low income immigrant families, such as the Temporary Assistance for Needy Families (TANF), the Children's Health Insurance Program (CHIP), the Supplemental Nutrition Assistance Program (SNAP), where African and Hispanic communities don't have knowledge about their existence and don't have representatives to assist them through the application process.

Finally, another contributor to this issue is their lack of assistance for even getting an application in their hands, so many won't know how to submit an application online, fill it out in person, or even be able to recruit documents necessary for their application. One suggestion for eliminating this barrier may be providing workshops at schools, community centers, or even libraries about free to low cost insurance programs that immigrant communities are eligible for. There's this misconception that citizenship status disqualifies them from any consideration for

programs like Covered California and Medical, but it's important to eliminate misinformation, and this can be done through community efforts. In partnership with health networks like Altamed, and increased funding for navigator programs, immigrant communities can ensure they know about qualified resources for mental health, health fairs, and even how to schedule visits to receive health services.

Transportation

Another contributor for the barriers in healthcare for immigrant groups is their lack of transportation towards doctors offices and appointments. This type of transportation insecurity is most specifically experienced by Hispanic and African immigrants such that in a 2017 report from the American Hospital Association, it was the main reason for no shows for important screening and diagnostic appointments (Nadeem & Nadeem, 2024). This is a precarious position because it can possibly lead to conditions deteriorating and developing into more expensive and severe illnesses. Public transport isn't always an option for those patients with disabilities, especially considering it can be time consuming, inconvenient, and sometimes even unsafe. Comprehending these genuine concerns can be draining both mentally and physically, especially vulnerable groups, is a part of respecting their dignity and meeting their needs. Efforts like Moving Clinics Upstream work in coalition with wellness centers, Planned Parenthood, and other clinics to address patient concerns, one including transportations (Nadeem & Nadeem, 2024). One solution to this could be more access to virtual check ins conducted by physicians so they avoid the trouble of travel, such as in the case of a testimony by Kheir Clinic Patient "my mental stability improves drastically, my physical condition too" (Nadeem & Nadeem, 2024). They don't worry about how they'll get to the appointment, nor will have to be anxious about the

trip towards it. Physical condition also improves because they save energy needed for recovery at home instead of making the trip to the hospital. Programs with van services for elderly, disabled immigrants could also meet their different needs without straining their money. Although not commonly thought about, reliable transportation is a significant barrier that prevents immigrants from receiving quality care they need for health outcomes and lifestyles.

Negative Experiences in Visits

Treating diverse disadvantaged immigrant populations entails establishing culturally and linguistically appropriate programs that consider cultural aspects and individual patient lifestyles, instead of treating the disease on its own. National surveys administered to immigrant families report negative experiences with healthcare providers and settings because of cultural differences and miscommunications (Okie, 2007). For example, in a survey conducted by Pew Research Center in 2021, Hispanic and Asians were asked to rate the quality of care they received during their visits with health care providers in the past six to twelve months. Around 56% of Hispanic and Asian Americans reported having very good/excellent care, while only 28% of Hispanic and Asian immigrants described it as good (Nadeem & Nadeem, 2024). Those with lower family income and no health insurance reported more frequent adverse experiences in the healthcare system, including having to speak up about low quality care they were receiving. For example, 32% claimed their health concerns were being dismissed by physicians and they'd be rushed out of facilities, which contributed to their perceptions of not being a priority to their doctors and never returning for further treatment (Nadeem & Nadeem, 2024). Close to 23% recalled not having their pain being taken seriously and being treated with less respect because of weight and eating habits.

This ties in with healthcare centers not having culturally appropriate personnel to treat the diverse communities they serve. For example, many Hispanic immigrants unfortunately have higher rates of obesity and being overweight, especially youth being disproportionately burdened with these hereditary conditions that are further propagated by systematic barriers that place them in food deserts (Aleman et al., 2023). This is a common theme also presented in African immigrants living in impoverished communities. Both African and Hispanic immigrants' health is affected by environmental influences, behavioral, and sociocultural factors that prevent them from maintaining healthy weight. Both groups have social norms that discourage them from reaching healthy lifestyles due to traditional cuisine that is high in saturated fats, calories, sodium, and sometimes very low in nutrients and balance (Aleman et al., 2023). Consumption of vegetables, fruits is little to none, so as age progresses, the development of weight related diseases like cholesterol, hypertension, and obesity is likely. These groups also commonly happen to live in "food deserts", which are defined as geographic areas where nourishing food (like farmer's markets) that is plentiful and affordable, is limited in access, possibly leading to nutritional deficiencies (Aleman et al., 2023). This lack of sufficient supply is actually replaced with fast food chains that surround their communities and seem more convenient to consume, and since these are sometimes the only items available, breaking these bad eating habits require a lot of comprehension and understanding from health professionals and the individuals themselves. For treatment like diabetes, physicians recommend strict dietary changes and don't take into consideration these health barriers that immigrants face, hence the criticism they reported during their recent doctor visits. In some of the testimonials of Hispanic immigrants, they reported feeling inferior when telling their physicians about their Guatemalan home remedies for things like chronic indigestion and cleansing of the digestive system, but

most importantly the important role that prayer had in their course of action for healing. Asian immigrants also reported feeling ridiculed or disrespected by medical personnel when communicating about their own efforts to cure their conditions with herbal teas, meditation, and losing their trust in their physician each time (Camp et al., 2022). They never seemed to be able to reach middle ground for a treatment regimen that fit their needs and incorporated their personal preferences in the approach, so they avoided assistance altogether.

I myself also grew up with this sense of mistrust for healthcare systems because I'd first hand witnessed my family members not being priorities for physicians, to them they were simply diseases, not whole humans that require being treated with respect and dignity. Not until I grew up did I break the chain and became more comfortable with the idea of being vulnerable with doctors because I knew they had some knowledge about my culture, its practices, and their effect on my health.

In addition, it's important to note that Asian immigrant women disproportionately die at a higher rate (1.5-1.7 times more) for breast cancer and other curable diseases when compared to other ethnic groups, often because of misdiagnosis (Camp et al., 2022). This trend also stands for serious STDs that infect Asian immigrant women at higher rates than other groups, yet fail to be detected in facilities. Additionally, in the U.S, suicide is one of the leading causes of death for Asian women for ages 15-24 (Camp et al., 2022). These illnesses and deteriorated health statuses for Asian women are a result of stereotypes that mask their symptoms, often leading doctors to miss them and not detect them at earlier stages. In this case, stereotypes that Asian women don't get STDs, breast cancer, and are the model minority, prevent physicians from addressing the illness and providing tests/treatment to identify them (Camp et al., 2022). These myths lead to

insufficient research that would otherwise improve medical services and treatments for these communities. This is why it's important to have culturally sensitive health programs and ethnically representative physicians that are ready to treat patients from diverse backgrounds, and essentially, being patient and comprehensive that there should be mutual trust and communication in order to achieve better health outcomes in the long run.

Physicians conversing with patients directly in their native language is also a rare occurrence for immigrants, so having translators communicate uncomfortable symptoms from patients can shape their experiences into tedious and frustrating ones, where even good bedside manner is absent (Camp et al., 2022). Many things can get lost in translation, so misunderstandings between families and physicians increase their inability to utilize medical advice appropriately and participate in medical procedures because English may not be their first language, or the terms are far too complex to understand. It often leads to their exclusion in diagnostic processes and lower life satisfaction because treatment regimens may be insensitive and non accommodating to traditional customs of the families (Salami et al., 2020). I recall being of young age and having to translate for my parents about critical illnesses they've had, so barely learning how to speak and having to carry the responsibility that their health was in your hands because if you mistranslated a few words, they could possibly misdiagnose and it would be beyond your control. These studies are of immense importance because they highlight that taking the time to build trust and educating themselves of patient cultural backgrounds will foster efficient patient-doctor relationships that prioritize health. It's also important to note that having culturally diverse medical personnel that is also linguistically diverse, can be a step forward to equitable health care experiences, as well as more funding achieved by campaigning and grass roots advocacy that could support a social justice agenda that improves accessibility to

medical services. This could also entail professional development for physicians to reflect on biases getting into their way of providing quality care for all, hiring more translators, or even themselves to deliver bilingual health care at arms reach.

Deportation

To further matters, Asian and Hispanic immigrant status derives fear of calling attention to immigration officials during their hospital stays, perpetuating their accessibility to healthcare (Salami et al., 2020). In a survey conducted in 2023, around ¼ of participants claimed that immigration related fears refrained them from applying for housing, low cost health services and nutrition related programs during the Trump Administration. Even 8% of the participants who had lawful status after being undocumented, still retained fear induced attitudes and worries about their participation deterring their eligibility for green card holding. Although insignificant to some, trauma and anxiety were legitimate feelings reported from these immigrant groups about simple things like participating in cashless assistance programs, fearing their information will help officials trace their location and motivate a deportation.

Barriers/ Influence on Mental Health

Accessibility and Language

Leaving their home countries, immigrant groups also leave behind social networks. Upon arriving in the United States, they then face exclusion across many contexts including sociocultural settings. In a diagnostic interview of Hispanic immigrants, 36% of the individuals had symptoms pertaining to at least one mental disorder (Bridges et al., 2012). The reason for these mental health challenges come from the alienation they felt as they tried

to assimilate and navigate an entirely different country (Berry & Hou, 2012). For them, linguistically appropriate and affordable accessibility for mental health services was diminished, so psychiatric assistance was something they failed to seek. A study found that only 1% of licensed psychologists spoke Spanish, so it's notable to say that service utilization is further perpetuated by systemic barriers that seem to not prioritize the emotional well being of immigrant families (Bridges et al., 2012). These findings are significant because they emphasize that the need for mental health services for immigrant communities is often overlooked and not considered a health priority by the U.S healthcare system.

Parenting Styles

In addition to children assimilating to new social norms and principles, Hispanic and Asian immigrant parents may also harbor feelings of inferiority or shame as their own parenting ideologies and practices are looked down on by more American health practitioners and other social networks. For example, both types of immigrant parents are commonly seen to use authoritative practices, where they expect strict obedience, are seen to make decisions for their children, and have little to no leniency, while Anglo views of parenting suggest one should let the child be autonomous, expressive and individualistic. In addition, Hispanic and African parents sometimes turn to physical punishment as a means of negative reinforcement to eliminate bad behavior, but these forms of discipline are widely frowned upon in American parents and even in organizations like the American Academy of Pediatrics. In a nationally representative sample conducted in 2021, 62% of participants in

the sample shamed parents who turned to spanking, and in the *Journal of Family Psychology*, close to eighty studies over the course of half a century had correlated physical punishment to the development of depression and aggressive tendencies in children. Hence, Hispanic and African parents constantly receive backlash and experience disconnection as their own parenting styles (even though done with the child's best intentions in mind) and family behaviors differ significantly, so intimidation and family focused interventions in programs at school or social services would be needed for optimal socialization and development of these communities (Berry & Hou, 2012).

Implications on Mental Health

Similarly, the pressures of being the child that breaks the cycle of poverty and achieves higher education also create mental health strains and forces these immigrant children to repress valid emotions of fear and anxiety (Bridges et al., 2012). Immigrant children must also balance school, family, and in many cases, work hours. The pressures to achieve the American Dream and make family sacrifices worth it may become further complicated if they are unable to find effective coping strategies, resources, and supportive peer groups. The systematic strategies to place lower class communities together also force immigrants to occupy high crime neighborhoods that increase the likelihood of accumulating negative emotions and frustration (Bridges et al., 2012). A study found that only 1% of licensed psychologists spoke Spanish, so it's notable to say that service utilization is further perpetuated by systemic barriers that seem to not prioritize the emotional well being of immigrant families (Bridges et al., 2012).

Barriers in Education

Implicit Bias in the Classroom

Understanding the role that ethnic identity and immigration status has on educational achievement and adjustment has been largely investigated by psychological researchers in an effort to maximize support and interventions. Attainment of higher education and upward social mobility is another goal that is rarely reached for immigrant families because of systemic barriers in education. “Stereotype” threat is defined as a position where individuals fear their actions will confirm negative stereotypes of their cultural or ethnic group, often leading to frustration and anxiety (Turney and Kao, 2009) In conjunction with this idea, immigrant children may also experience “imposter syndrome”, which is defined as a person’s inability to be convinced that despite their high performing skills and achievements, they aren’t worthy of the positions they hold and shouldn’t occupy that space (Turney and Kao, 2009). These ideas disguised behind social racism and discrimination create burdens for immigrant students to succeed in academic settings and have negative implications on their motivation. Implicit bias from educators can also be perceived by immigrant children, where the educators’ prejudices and differing expectations for achievement of ethnic students motivate them to provide differential treatment and support. Their tendencies may be to dismiss bad behavior from ethnic minority of immigrant children because they are seen as “troubled”, so they rarely set forth educational challenges that could be enriching for their education (Turney and Kao, 2009). This results in immigrant children, especially those with Hispanic and African descent, to be less engaged and focused in the classroom, less likely to seek help from their educator, and less likely to participate in educational enrichment activities that could help them develop study and beneficial academic skills (Turney and Kao, 2009). This can lead to a cycle of low academic preparation where

immigrant students are less likely to be placed in honors courses, have decreased aspirations to attend college, and even less preparation once it's time to enter higher education.

Immigrant parents' involvement in their children's education is seemingly decreased in these households because of the hostility from educators or educational facilities that fail to create a welcoming environment for them (Langenkamp, 2019). The language barriers also pose limits to their involvement and prevent positive relationship building with school personnel. These relationships are extremely important for parents to track and understand the academic progress of their students. This further results in potentially negative behavioral and academic outcomes throughout the educational journeys of immigrant children (Turney & Kao, 2009). Although there is little research on experiences during early childhood for immigrant children, it seems evident that if children perceive little interest from their parents in their school activities, they themselves will value education at a lower level (Turney, & Kao, 2009).

Recent interviews reveal that while immigrant parents have high academic aspirations for their children, only about $\frac{1}{3}$ of these children actually reach higher education (Langenkamp, 2019). This is due to a lack of social capital, residential segregation towards schools with limited resources and educational opportunities, and structural barriers in college systems that lower their chances of getting admitted (Langenkamp, 2019).

In terms of financial assistance for education, immigrant families face many barriers. For some immigrant families, they are unable to pay for college education because of thresholds on financial aid forms and lack of expertise and guidance about the application process. Another significant barrier is that only few families are able to receive federal funding and at the state level due to citizenship status, leaving them out of federal grants and opportunities that citizens do have access to (Langenkamp, 2019). This research is significant because it provides a

background about the cycle of inequality that further perpetuates their lack of economic statuses and social standing. They also shed light as to how institutions can make adjustments that can empower immigrants to pursue higher education. Educating and ensuring that based on the student population, there is personnel at schools to meet linguistic diversity, and cultural needs for different students at school is also key.

Barriers in the workforce

Finally, systemic barriers in the workforce further decrease life satisfaction and influence the personal experiences of Hispanic and Asian immigrants. These groups are often left with no choice but to occupy poverty wage jobs where close to $\frac{3}{4}$ fail to abide by state health laws, so exposing them to dangerous conditions where they're at higher risk for stress injuries, respiratory impairments due to inadequate ventilation, and toxic exposure that can lead to neurological impairments.

Asian immigrants have reported sexual harassment in the workplace, as well as exploitation, and a lack of access to occupational training and education for these groups accounts for the self sufficient that is rarely reached. A study investigated the barriers these communities face, and found that their professional skills, contribution to taxes, and productivity are often overlooked by their host country, so these jobs ultimately create stress in their material well being and physical health (Heilbrunn et al., 2010). Their jobs also make less accommodations when they need to attend to medical or educational appointments for their children, so this cycle results in low involvement in their child's life and may create tension or strains in the family unit and stability (Heilbrunn et al., 2010). In other cases, the language barriers, lack of educational preparation available to them, and lack of policies that incorporate

them into the labor market, leads to long term unemployment and ultimately, a cycle of poverty that further poses strain to the family unit (Heilbrunn et al., 2010).

Although lack of professional skills contribute greatly, it is possible that stereotypes and discrimination also play a role in the negative experiences in the labor force for immigrants. These studies examining the experiences of immigrant families reveal that their incorporation to a new country includes many inevitable hardships that may be detrimental to their psychological well being and social experiences.

Conclusion

Extensive research and studies have analyzed post-migration experiences and make note of the systemic barriers the host country creates to the experiences and wellbeing of immigrant groups, including children and families of Hispanic, Asian, and African descent. Some of these barriers exist in healthcare, ranging from ineligibility for insurance programs, low quality care that isn't culturally or linguistically competent, and even transportation conflicts that prevent them from attending doctor appointments. It's important to raise awareness about these issues because it accounts for the deteriorated health outcomes that Hispanic, Asian, and African immigrant groups experience. It was also notable to cover the barriers that these groups face in educational settings, such as not having multicultural, bilingual instruction that fits their individual needs, or even accounts for their disadvantaged position for education. As noted in the research, educational barriers even extend toward higher grades, accounting for their low access to financial aid, and even stereotypes/discrimination that creates feelings of inferiority in the spaces they occupy. This would be shown to further tie into the process of applying for jobs, where despite having good qualifications and skills, they'd be stuck with low paying jobs with

little room for social mobility. Through education and a social justice agenda for implementing new policies that target these systemic barriers directly, we can be responsive to the needs of these immigrant groups and increase their accessibility to social services they can greatly benefit from. Unfortunately, these barriers did show a significant influence in the mental health of Hispanic and African immigrants, where anxiety and frustration were prevalent as they navigated different social systems. This issue of social injustice calls for attention, as well as raising awareness for courses of action in these institutions that could be beneficial for everyone.

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